

NON-VERBAL COMMUNICATION IN THE ASPECT OF TEACHER'S PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7185881>

Abstract:At present ,on the pages of psychological and pedagogical literature,much attention is paid to the problem of communication in professional and pedagogical activities.One of the aspects of this problem is the study of the non-verbal component.From this point of view,the article discusses non-verbal communication in the aspect of teacher's pedagogical activity during the lesson .

Key words: non-verbal communication, gesture, facial expressions, intonation,posture,gaze,manner of listening,non-speech components.

The content of the teacher's work is to promote the mental development of the student,and the main 'tool'is his mental interaction with the child pedagogical communication.Communication is a necessary and special condition for the child to appropriate the achievements of the historical development of mankind.The interaction between the student and the teacher consists,first of all ,in the exchange between them of information of a cognitive and affective evaluative nature.And the transfer of this information is carried out both verbally and through various means of non-verbal communication.Communicating with students,the teacher receives a significant part of the information regarding their emotional state,intention,attitudes towards something not from the words of the students but from gestures,facial expressions,intonation,posture gaze,manner of listening.

There are many instructional approaches for helping English language learners improve both reading comprehension and overall language proficiency. One such approach, the literature circle-which is somewhat like a student book club in the classroom-has drawn a great deal of attention in recent years . Many teachers champion the strategy and use it consistently in their classrooms .

According to the Standards for the English focused on the chosen book. Examples of Language Arts published by the International Reading Association and National Council of Teachers of English (1996, 32), the instructional practices realized by literature circles embody quality educational standards and are used by teachers "who are bringing out the best in their students day by day."To shed light on the many ways that literature circles improve English skills, this article defines the term, provides a brief theoretical foundation for the

use of literature circles, describes their benefits, and then presents a four-lesson unit that applies the approach to the teaching of a literary text.

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A literature circle is an activity in which members meet to discuss and respond to a book that they are all reading . As Cameron et al. (2012) explain, literature circles are led mostly by students, while the teacher remains in the background and performs only basic control functions. Roles are usually assigned to members of the literature circle to allow the group to function productively and to help members remain five individual roles are Discussion Director, Literary Luminary, Illustrator, Summarizer, and Vocabulary Enricher (Daniels and Steineke 2004). The Discussion Director's task, for example, could be to develop at least five questions about the text and then share these questions with the group. The Literary Luminary pinpoints important parts of the text for the group in order to stimulate thinking and elicit some interesting facts about the text. The Illustrator's job might be to draw pictures related to the reading and share the drawings with the group; the group members then speculate on the meaning of the pictures and connect them to their own ideas about the text. The Summarizer's role is to recall what happened in the reading and prepare a summary for the group, and the Vocabulary Enricher helps the group find and discuss new or difficult words (Daniels and Steineke 2004). These roles can rotate with each discussion so that every student has the opportunity to perform each role. Overall, the purpose of the literature circle is to support student language improvement, particularly through reading comprehension and vocabulary learning.

Benefits of literature circles. Recent evidence demonstrates that literature circles positively impact student learning processes and language development. Much of this impact is directed towards several important areas for language learning, including the following.

Improved comprehension skills: Most important of all the benefits, literature circles help students develop comprehension skills that are essential when reading a text. Literature circles support strategies such as visualizing, connecting, questioning, inferring, and analyzing that are vital to solid comprehension and lively conversation.

Since the assigned roles in literature circles require students to draw the events, create questions, and summarize the text, learners are called upon to use a variety of strengths and skills to prepare for the discussion. As students perform their roles, they draw information from the text, pay attention to details to support their ideas, highlight main ideas, and respond critically to what they have read by making judgments about the characters' intentions and actions, and about how and why things happened in the story.

Enhanced responsibility and motivation: Another benefit of literature circles is helping students feel a sense of ownership and responsibility. Student choice and social interaction easily integrate into literature circles, which support student motivation and can have a very powerful effect on achievement. Researchers have also found that when students work in collaborative groups they encourage each other's efforts and that this leads to increased motivation and effort.

Expanded collaborative discussion: Reading specialists highlight discussion, student response, and collaboration as important aspects of literature circles for providing a way for students to engage in critical thinking and reflection. When students learn a second language, collaborative discussions with peers often play a vital role in reinforcing comprehension skills because the active involvement that takes place entails speaking.

References:

1. Khalilova H.Kh. Features of teaching the English language at the economic university. EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR) - Peer Reviewed Journal Volume: 7 | Issue: 2 | February
2. Andreev A. V. "Practice of the electronic education" Moscow, p-510 -2008y.
3. 2022 Жалолов 'Тил ва талимнинг мазмуни ва мохияти 1993'.

